

Thracian Rolligeras=Hot Spring: Rolli=Hot; Geras=Water-Spring; in Rolisteneas: Roli-= “blood” or “the red Yang force” or something similar to the latter; a Geras meaning “water-spring” was already known to be present in Germigeras in Dacia; Ancient Greek *rhóa* (=pomegranate fruit) is from a **h₁rew-* root that meant “red; hot; burning; the Yang force”

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Abstract

In this paper I propose that the *Rolli-* in the Thracian/Paeonian toponym *Rolligeras* quite certainly means “hot”, from a root that meant “hot, burning, pungent”, with additional semantics possible in the root and likely present in the root. In the putative anthroponym Rolisteneas (a Thracian/Paeonian or Greco-Thracian/Greco-Paeonian anthroponym), *Roli-* likely meant “blood”, which would have developed from “red” and from “hot” (blood is red and warm, and full of a warm active energy), with “red” developing from “burning”.

For this *Rolli-* and *Roli-*, I propose a root **h₁rew-*, “burning, hot”, further back possibly/very likely meaning something like “virile energy (the yang force, as the Chinese call it: the yang force is colored red and identified with the sun)”. The extended form of **h₁rew-* is the well-known PIE **h₁rewd^h-* “red”.

That *geras* in *Germigeras* means “water-spring” has already been implied or explicitly articulated in works by other authors published many years before this paper, based on the 100% identification of *Germigeras* with *Germisara*, a Dacian toponym known to be the name of an important hot spring in Dacia/Roman Dacia. *Germisara/Germigeras*=”Hot Spring” to a 100% certainty, because:

1) the forms *Germ-/Garm-/Gorm-* meaning “warm, hot” are already known in other Indo-European languages, deriving from the PIE root **g^{wh}er-* “warm, hot”, from where Ancient Greek θερμός (“warm, hot” etc.) derives, and probably also English “warm” and its Germanic cognates derive from **g^{wh}er-* as well.

2) The site of *Germisara/Germigeras/Zermizeras* (etc.) is a thermal¹ water-spring site, used as hot baths in Pre-Roman and Roman times and afterwards;

and 3) because Dacian “sara” fits the PIE root **ser*, “to flow, to run” without a problem.

But I have not seen any work 1) articulating the idea that the *geras* in *Rolligeras* means “water-spring”; nor did I see any work 2) pointing out that we find *geras* in the Thracian/Paeonian toponym *Rolligeras* and in the Dacian toponym *Germigeras* attested in Anonymous of Ravenna: I have seen no work mentioning both toponyms in the same paper. If these two things have not occurred in any previous works, this paper corrects those two big oversights from previous scholars.

1 In case any readers don’t know, English thermal, thermo- etc. derive from Ancient Greek θερμός .

In this paper, I also offer an etymology for Geras in the toponyms, an etymology which probably does not include Sara (which is likely not a satemized variant of Geras, but may be), but might include Zera(s), if Zera(s) is a satemized variant of Geras. Zera(s) may instead be a variant and cognate of Sara, and both Zera(s) and Sara may not be cognate with Geras. Dacian Sara “water-spring” has already been theorized by previous authors to derive from PIE *ser, “to flow, to run”: this Dacian Sara probably does derive from *ser, “to flow, to run”, unless it is a satemized variant of Geras.

A little over a month after publishing the first draft of this paper on December 2nd, 2023, I rediscovered (having seen them a number of times over the past years, having probably first seen them in 2005 or 2006) the Dacian toponyms *Germisara*, *Germizeras*, *Zermizeras* and *Germigeras* (variant forms for the same toponym location); during the time that I was (occasionally) working on the etymology of *Rolligeras* (that work resulting in the first draft of this paper on Dec 2nd, 2023), I had forgotten about those *Germisara*, *Germizeras*, *Zermizeras* and *Germigeras* toponyms. I found them again in January or February 2024.

Part 1:

Back in 2021 and continuing into most of 2023, I posited that the Roli- in the Thracian (or Paeonian? Or Greco-Thracian if “steneas” is from Greek, or Greco-Paeonian?) anthroponym Rolisteneas² meant “blood”, and I based that principally on the Rol- form beginning with Ro-, because there are a number of words beginning with Ro- and meaning “red”, and they are known to derive from PIE *h₁rewd^h-, which meant “red”.

I later deduced/theorized that the Ancient Greek word *ῥοιλιαῖς*=“biting, pungent” (attested in Hesychius of Alexandria’s glossary, he gives *ῥοιλιαῖς*=δάκναις; and the word δάκναις =“biting, pungent”: and had other adjacent meanings as well, but it is not necessary to enumerate those now) derives from **ῥοιλιαῖς*=“hot, burning” (as we see with the meanings of the German word *beißen*, which means “to bite; to burn; to sting; to be sharp; to be spicy”), and the meaning “red” easily develops from “hot, burning”, and the meaning “blood” can easily develop from “red, hot”, since blood is red when outside of the body, and warm. So I proposed in 2021 that Roli=“blood” and I still think that is very likely, but it may be that Roli=“Fiery strength”, “Yang strength” (the red Yang of the Chinese Yin and Yang; Yang is identified with red, heat, light, the sun and the male gender), something like that. And I proposed in 2021 that Thracian Roli- in Rolisteneas is cognate with Ancient Greek *ῥοιλιαῖς*=“biting, pungent” and that is what I propose in this paper as well, both deriving from **h₁rew-*“red; burning, hot, pungent”.

Compare how in Ancient Greek, θερμός has the meanings “warm, hot, boiling, glowing, hot-headed, hasty, rash, headstrong, eager, active, fresh”---all these meanings attested for one word, θερμός in Ancient Greek times.

For the phonetic/phonological “Rol ~ Roil” variance across Thracian and Greek, compare how in current Greek we find ρόδι (pomegranate) with a colloquial variant ρόιδι (pomegranate) and another variant ρόιδο (pomegranate).

² Most likely an anthroponym, though attested in an inscription that has no word breaks. The inscription is on a gold ring found near Ezerovo in the Plovdiv region of Bulgaria in 1912.

With the element *steneas* in *Rolisteneas* most likely meaning “strong” as in Ancient Greek σθένης (*sthenēs*)/σθένος (*sthenos*), so I proposed beginning in 2021 that *Rolisteneas*=”Of Strong Blood”, but beginning in this paper I also propose that *Rolisteneas* could have meant “Of Strong Yang Force”, or something similar to that.

My rediscovery in January or February 2024 of those Dacian toponyms named above (*Germisara*, *Germizeras*, *Zermizeras* and *Germigeras*) showed me that *Geras*=”water-spring”, and showed me that *Rolli* describes something about the water-spring. In January or February 2024 in comments that I posted publicly on Academia.edu, comments which I have taken screenshots of for the historical record, I first published my observation that the *Geras* in *Rolligeras* means “water-spring” (if no one has stated this before, then I was the first to do so at that time).

It was in 2023 that I began working on deciphering the Thracian/Paeonian toponym *Rolligeras* found in Procopius’ *De Aedificiis*, book 4.

In Thracian and in Dacian and in Paeonian and in Illyrian, etc., I looked for and noted down any forms close to the *Rolli*- in Thracian/Paeonian toponym *Rolligeras*: from memory, I knew that the *Rolli*- in *Rolligeras* is similar to the *Roli*- in *Rolistene(as)* and similar to the Thracian/Getic/Dacian anthroponym *Ῥώλης* (romanized as *Rholes/Roles*; *Ῥώλης* is a Getae chieftain mentioned by the Ancient Roman author Dio Cassius in his *Roman History*) and the Dacian anthroponym *Rolouzis*³ (*Rolouzis* is attested on ostracons of Dacian cavalry recruited after the Roman conquest and stationed in East Egypt, see Dan Dana, 2003, pg. 179; *Rolouzis* in my opinion is possibly a compound with “*zis*” meaning “god”, known from other Daco-Thracian material); looking through linguistic works on Thracian and Getic/Dacian, I found no mention of any additional forms of this nature, aside from possibly *Rolis/Rholis* as variant of *Rholes/Roles*.

The toponym *Rolligeras* was located in Southwestern Bulgaria⁴, while *Ezerovo*, where the inscribed ring was found, is in the Plovdiv region, which is in South-Central Bulgaria, immediately east of Southwestern Bulgaria.

It is very likely that in all the forms cited in the paragraph above, we are dealing with the same word. Let us now employ my theory described above about *Roli*=”blood” coming from “red” and “hot”, from a root that meant “hot, burning, yang force”:

let us employ that theory because in the portion of the manuscript where Procopius mentions *Rolligeras*, we find other hot spring toponyms listed by Procopius in the same geographical area where he says *Rolligeras* was located (and where I later verified that hot springs are still to be found to this day), so, considering everything that I describe in this paper, I propose that the *Rolli*- of *Rolligeras* means “Hot

3 For the Dacian/Getic male anthroponym *Ῥώλης* (and also attested as *Rolis*?) and for the Dacian *Rolouzis*, I posited and published beginning in 2021 that these names all meant “virile, potent, boisterous, strong-blooded”, and I still think that is either correct or very close to correct. It is also possible of course that *Roles/Rholes* and/or *Rolouzis* are unrelated to the *Rolli*- in *Rolligeras*, but I favor the scenario that they are versions of the same word, along with the *Roli*- in *Rolisteneas*. The Daco-Getic (and Thracian?) male names *Oroles*, *Orola* (both *Oroles* and *Orola* are attested as men's names) probably have a different etymology.

4 See Peter Delev. A History of the Tribes of South-Western Thrace in the First Millennium B.C. Sofia, St. Kliment Ohridski University Publishing House, 2014 (Summary in English), page 9: in the subsection “Cities”, in the section “Geographical Overview”.

Spring”, with Rolli=”Hot”, and Geras meaning “water-spring” (as we find in Dacian the toponym Germigeras, where Geras means “water-spring”)⁵.

As I mention in the paragraph above, I checked to see whether there are hot springs/thermal baths in Southwestern Bulgaria, and I found this quote:

“ “Where to find the hot springs in Bulgaria?” is a question we almost always hear. Our answer is Blagoevgrad! This picturesque province of Southwestern Bulgaria is home to a myriad of hot springs, most found near the Pirin mountains. Three villages in the area, Bansko, Banya and Dobrinishte, are known for their booming thermal hotel industry.” “

Here are the other hot spring toponyms mentioned by Procopius in the exact short portion where he mentions Rolligeras, and anyone who reads the manuscript will see that Procopius is saying that those toponyms are close to Rolligeras: the toponyms are Germas and Germente. Here is an English translation of that portion of Procopius’ De Aedificiis:

“Near the city Germente, Scaplizo was built new, and the following were restored:

Germas

Candaras

Rolligeras

Scinzerias

Rhiginocastellum

Suegogmense”

See: https://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/E/Roman/Texts/Procopius/Buildings/4B*.html

Procopius, when listing the Roman/Byzantine forts built and rebuilt under the reign of Justinian in Book 4 of his De Aedificiis, did not specify many details, such as what the toponyms mean, nor such niceties as what things were notable in the environs of the forts---maybe a few times he did that, but if so those are exceptions to the laconic rule in his long list of forts. The mention in my quote above (“This picturesque province of Southwestern Bulgaria is home to a myriad of hot springs, most found near the Pirin mountains”) of hot springs located near mountains suggests a foothill, hill or mountain where a Roman fort was built, a fort and hill located near a thermal bath/hot spring.

In the Part 2 of this paper I will go into a more detailed treatment of the Rolli- portion of Rolligeras. But now I will offer an etymology (or two etymologies) for Dacian and Thracian Geras=”hot spring”. I do not think that the hard G sound of Geras can derive from PIE *ser- “to flow,

⁵ In the first draft of this paper, having forgotten about the Dacian toponyms detailed in this paper, I hypothesized that Geras in Rolligeras means “hot”, deriving from PIE *g^{wh}er- “warm, hot”, but I am now sure that that is not so. Phonetically/phonologically there is no problem, since we find Germe/Germis (cf. Germidava, Germetitha, Germisara, etc.) in Dacian and Thracian meaning “hot, warm”, and Geras could have been a Thracian/Dacian by-form of Germe/Germis, as we find θερρω and θερρέω and θερμός (etc.) as by-forms in Ancient Greek, all deriving from PIE *g^{wh}er- “warm, hot”. But Germigeras and Germisara show that Geras means “water-spring”, not “hot” nor “warm”.

to run” and I think most Indo-European linguists and Daco-Thracological linguists will agree with me about that.

So from what root does Daco-Thracian Geras=“water-spring” derive? My preferred option is my theory that it derives from the same root from which Albanian *ger* (plural *gera*) meaning “squirrel” derives. Vladimir Orel (apparently following Fraenkel, 140; and Pokorny I 397-398) in his etymological dictionary of much of the Albanian lexicon states that Albanian *gera* (“squirrel”) comes from a reconstructed Proto-Albanian **gaura*, a reconstruction based partly on theories about Albanian to Proto-Albanian sound-shifts, but primarily based on the theory (taken from Fraenkel and Pokorny? Orel cites these two sources for his etymology) that the Albanian word derives from the meaning “furry” and is cognate with Lithuanian *gauras* “hair, down, tuft of hair” and Latvian *gauri* “pubic hair”, and with Middle Irish *gúaire* “hair”⁶.

Since a number of words meaning “furry” and “hair” derive from the meaning “to grow out” or from the meaning “to spring up”, those meanings both---especially “to spring up”---fit excellently as the root-meaning for a word attested/deciphered as meaning “water-spring”. Phonologically though, does **gaur-* seem like a likely source for a Daco-Thracian *ger-*? I’m not sure, because so little is known about Thracian sound-shifts from their root-words. Semantically though it is so appealing, beyond the fur springing out on a squirrel’s bushy tail: see also the way the squirrels’ tails are held erect, their tails springing up; the way squirrels spring up trees so fast. The native squirrels of Europe, the red squirrels (*Sciurus vulgaris*)---the ones that concern us etymologically in this paper, because they were actually there and they were the squirrels that were named *ger/gera*--even have very high prominent pointy ears that stand erect.

Another possibility for Daco-Thracian *geras*=“water-spring” is a derivation from a PIE **g^her-* “to protrude, to project; to have protrusions” (which could be from an earlier “to spring up, to spring out”), see Latvian *zars* meaning “branch; twig; spray of a plant”, the “spray of a plant” being the part that grows from the stem or trunk and supports leaves, and the term can include the leaves as well. PIE **g^her*, as far as the initial **g^h-* at least, fits the initial *g-* sound encountered in Albanian, Lithuanian, Latvian and Middle Irish, according to references I checked. But the “au” of the Baltic and Irish words (and of the hypothetical Proto-Albanian **gaura*) might not be compatible with a **g^her* root : this is something to find out for the next edition.

I have found that the Albanian word “*varr/vorr*” meaning “grave” is theorized by Demiraj to derive from a Proto-Albanian **āur(V)n* , in turn from PIE **h₁er-* , “earth”. However, that is a HeR root, not a CeR root, and I’m not sure if that works for a CeR root in Albanian. In Albanian, “au” after a consonant usually comes from a PIE “eu”.

Part 2: further details about **h₁rew-* “hot, burning; the yang force”

⁶ See: Orel, Vladimir (1998), *Albanian Etymological Dictionary*, Leiden, Boston, Köln: Brill, pg. 112.

So Thracian Roli- and Rolli- derive from a root **h₁rew-*, and do not derive from **hréyyō*, a Proto-Greek word which derives from PIE **srew-*, “to flow, stream, rush”; and Thracian Roli- and Rolli- are not cognate to the following Ancient Greek words which derive from PIE **srew*, “to flow”: *ρέω* (*rhéō*)=“I flow, stream, rush, gush”; *ῥεῦμα* (*rheûma*)=“stream, flow, current”; *ῥεῦσις* (*rheûsis*)=“flowing”; *ῥύσις* (*rhûsis*)=“flow; the course of a river or stream”; *ῥοή* (*rhoē*)=“a river, a stream”. And phonologically that would not have been likely either, because there is no reason to suppose that PIE **sr-* became **hr-* in Proto-Thracian/Thracian: I doubt that PIE **sr-* would become **hr-* in Proto-Thracian because the name of the Thracian river Στῤῥυμών (*Strūmōn*) by linguistic consensus derives from Thracian, due to its beginning with Str-, not with Hr- or Rh- as in Proto-Greek (Hr-) and Ancient Greek (Rh-).

So Thracian Rolli- and Roli- are not cognate with those Ancient Greek words deriving from **srew-*, but Thracian Rolli- and Roli- are cognate with Ancient Greek *ῥοιλιαῖς* which meant δάκναις (=“biting, pungent”), and I further propose that Ancient Greek *ῥόα* (*rhóa*)=“pomegranate fruit; pomegranate tree” is cognate with Thracian Rolli/Roli, because my developed theory is that *ῥόα* (*rhóa*)/ *ῥοιά* / *ῥοιή* =“pomegranate fruit, pomegranate tree” derives from “red”, from **h₁rew-*“red, burning, hot; the Yang force”. And from **h₁rew-*“red” I also derive *ῥοιά* meaning ‘mulberry’ (mulberries come in red and dark red and black varieties).

it had been previously suggested by a previous linguist that *ῥόα* (*rhóa*)/ *ῥοιά* / *ῥοιή* =“pomegranate fruit; pomegranate tree” derives from PIE **srew-* “to flow” because of the juice of the pomegranate fruit; that theory was good for its time, but it never became widely accepted; I’m now certain that it is incorrect. I’m also certain that another previous theory proposed by another linguist, that *ῥόα* is cognate with Ancient Greek *χρoιά* (*khroιά*) meaning “skin” (which would refer to the rind of the pomegranate: another theory that was good for its time) is certainly incorrect.

I also expect that Ancient Greek *ῥοιάς* meaning “*Papaver rhoeas*”, the common red poppy of Europe and elsewhere, derives from a root **h₁rew-* “to burn; hot, red”.

Above, we saw *ῥοιλιαῖς*=δάκναις =“biting, pungent” vis-a-vis *ῥοιά* / *ῥοιή* / *ῥόα* =“pomegranate fruit”; now see *ῥοιδνας*=δάκνας=“biting, pungent” vis--a-vis *ῥοῖδιον*=“small pomegranate”; *ῥοιδάριον*=“red rouge/red lipstick/a red cosmetic”; and Modern Greek *ρόδι* (*ródi*) and Romanian *rodie* both mean “pomegranate (fruit)”, while *rodiu* means “pomegranate tree” in Romanian and *ροδιά* (*rodiá*) means “pomegranate tree” in Modern Greek, and earlier I detailed the colloquial Modern Greek variant *ροῖδι* (pomegranate) and another variant *ροῖδο* (pomegranate).

ῥοιδαμός=*asparagus*, and I interpret *ῥοιδαμός* as deriving from “pungent”, because eating asparagus gives urine a very pungent smell, more pungent than the usual smell of urine. This interpretation is backed up by *ῥοιδνας*=δάκνας=“biting, pungent”. So it seems like *ῥοῖδιον*=“small pomegranate” and *ῥοιδάριον*=“red rouge/red lipstick/a red cosmetic”; and Modern Greek *ρόδι* (*ródi*) and Romanian *rodie* “pomegranate (fruit)” and Romanian *rodiu* “pomegranate tree” and *ροδιά* (*rodiá*) “pomegranate tree” in Modern Greek, and the colloquial Modern Greek variant *ροῖδι* (pomegranate) and another Modern Greek variant *ροῖδο* all derive from a *roid/rod*=“biting, pungent, red<burning, hot”, perhaps from a **h₁rewd* form.

For my etymology of *ῥοιδαμός*, a word referring to asparagus, see how Ancient Greek *δαῦκον* / *δαῦκος* referring to carrots and to close relatives of carrots, is theorized to be akin to *δαίω* =“to burn, to blaze, to light up, to kindle, to set on fire”, because some close relatives of carrots---and

they look very similar to carrots---have a pungent, burning taste; plus actual carrots are orange (which makes them rather flame-colored).

English “roil” meaning “to seethe; bubble; to render turbid by stirring”, etc., is of uncertain etymology and may be another cognate to *ῥοιλιαῖς*, if the earlier meaning of “roiling” was “boiling”, in turn from the meaning “burning”.

There is also a PIE **h₂réw-ōy-* “sun, sunshine”, which derives from PIE **h₂rew-* “to shine”, and all the forms in this paper that I posit as deriving from a PIE **h₁rew-* may derive instead from PIE **h₂rew-*; this is a question for the next edition, as if the question of whether at a Pre-PIE level, **h₂rew-*, **h₁rew-* and **h₁rewd^h* are all variants.

In January or February 2024, after I once again found Germisara, I got the idea that the Thracian name of a king, Saratokos/Saratakos, likely meant “Of Celebrated Pedigree”, since the element “takos”, “tokos” most likely, according to many Thracologists, meant “famous, renowned, celebrated”; and since Sara=“water-spring, water-source” in Dacian, and since words meaning “water-spring”/“water-source” usually give rise to the more general meanings “source, origin, pedigree”. I first published this theory of mine that Saratakos/Saratokos meant “Of Celebrated Pedigree/Of Renowned Origin” in a comment of mine on Academia.edu in January or February 2024, and I have the screenshots to prove it.

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